

Smart Insoles With Textile Capacitive Sensors for Efficient Gait Phase Recognition

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Abstract—Gait analysis is important in understanding human movement and diagnosing various mobility-related disorders. A crucial step in this procedure is the recognition of the different phases of human gait. An innovative, cost-effective prototype of shoe insoles with sensors is presented, designed to capture data which are used for gait phase recognition with the aid of artificial intelligence. Each insole is embedded with capacitive sensors to record measurements and is accompanied by an inertial measurement unit (IMU) that monitors foot motion during walking. Using these prototypes, we collected data from multiple volunteers, while they performed simple walking exercises. The collected data, having undergone preprocessing, were used to train a long short-term memory (LSTM)-based neural network that recognizes the different gait phases during walking. The resulting model can segment a gait session into distinct phases with high accuracy, effectively demonstrating the capability of the prototype pair of insoles to be used as an inexpensive way to record data that can be used for gait analysis. The presented method has potential applications in rehabilitation and the early detection of mobility impairments. The most important benefit of the developed system is that it constitutes an affordable alternative to commercial solutions for patients who require medical care through telemedicine.

Index Terms—Capacitive textile sensors, gait phase recognition, insoles, long short-term memory (LSTM).

I. INTRODUCTION

GAIT analysis is a fundamental tool in clinical practice that offers insights into human movement patterns and enables the diagnosis and management of mobility disorders. Especially for neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease, as well as stroke, which

deteriorate a person's walking ability [1], gait analysis helps medical professionals assess a patient's situation and give proper instructions for ongoing rehabilitation. In general, there is a rising demand for rehabilitation services that traditional healthcare systems cannot sustainably meet due to cost constraints and resource limitations, partly due to the increased life expectancy. Tele-rehabilitation offers a solution by enabling remote services through wearable sensors and digital technologies, potentially reducing costs, improving patient engagement [2].

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Gait rehabilitation may benefit from such services that assist clinicians in their jobs, by delivering reliable gait data, without delays, skipping the need for a live assessment by medical professionals. The cornerstone of such systems is gait phase recognition, which is the automated process of segmenting human gait in distinct phases, whose characteristics can be further analyzed to deduce insights.

Advancements in wearable technology during the last two decades have paved the way for innovative solutions, particularly in the form of insoles with embedded sensors [3], [4].

These have the potential to capture plantar pressure readings, which are then used, along with motion data from inertial measurement units (IMUs), for gait phase recognition. Plantar pressure is deduced in existing literature by using different types of sensors. Among them, piezoresistive is the most dominant type of sensor due to its reliability [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. Some of these methods benefit from the use of specific sensor manufacturing techniques for increased plantar pressure resolution [10], [11]. Piezoelectric sensors have also been used in combination with piezoresistive [12], but also on their own through printed prototype sensor arrays [13], [14], having the added benefit of operating without external power supply. Capacitive sensors [15], [16] have also been used, in some cases with the extra novelty of combining them with kinetic energy harvesters to remove the need for an external source of power [17], but also pressure sensors that utilize air bladders [18] from soft silicone have been proposed. A popular practice has been to include extrasensory systems in the form of IMUs [8], [9], [10], [19], [20], [21] to measure the angular velocity and acceleration, while the data are usually sent wirelessly over Bluetooth [6], [7], [8], [10], [21], [22], [23] or Wi-Fi [19], [24].

Insoles with embedded sensors have been simply presented [13], [22] and in some cases also compared against existing, well-established systems like the *F-scan* [25] and the *Footscan* [7], but in most cases, they were used to produce data for further analysis. Initially, they had been utilized to solve the gait phase recognition problem using algorithms based on rules [5], [12], [26] or fuzzy logic [18] during the 2000s. More recently, sensorized insoles have also been proposed to solve the more complicated and semantically elevated problem of human activity recognition. Machine learning methods, such as support vector machines [6], [7], [10], [27], [28], nearest neighbors [8], [17], [21], [29], and Gaussian Naive-Bayes [15], [23] among others, have been used, as well as deep learning approaches in the form of simple [29] and recurrent neural networks [20].

A considerable part of the reviewed literature is based on commercially available sensors, which are more expensive, due to their electronic components, compared to textile sensors. Fiber electronics have been the focus of research for the past two decades and have been used in multiple applications [30]. The effort started with the work of Scilingo et al. [31] who developed textile strain sensors by coating threads of fabric with a conductive polymer material. More recently, smart textiles have been fabricated using fibers made of graphene oxide/polyurethane using microfluidic spinning [32]. Graphene has also been used in coating, providing conductive capabilities in multilayered insoles that have been developed to monitor abnormal plantar pressure related to diabetic foot ulcers [33]. This work was further improved later, reducing sensor response time and enhancing compression-tensile sensitivity and pressure range while also optimizing the fabrication process, though the weight issue remained unresolved [34]. Another graphene-based approach was developed by Zhang et al. [35] where a leather fabric piezoresistive sensor was sprayed with graphene coating to achieve increased response and sensitivity properties in monitoring human physiological activity while noting performance limitations under

specific temperature and humidity conditions. In the latter works, graphene-based coating has been utilized to achieve greater performance at a higher production cost. Textile sensors made of fibers wrapped in a carbon nanotube-based thin film have also been developed to quantify ground reaction forces during walking [36]. In this case, the unit cost has been reported to be low, around U.S. \$50, while providing an ultrawide sensing range and a straightforward calibration method.

The use of core-sheath coaxial structure in fibers was mentioned in the work of Wang et al. [37] who used silver-coated nylon yarn as the core to create textiles made of piezoresistive yarn for monitoring human motion, body posture, or plantar pressure. Their work showed robust mechanical properties, producing stable results after 1200 cycles, high sensitivity, fast response time, and low industrial-scale manufacturing cost. Similarly, piezoresistive sensors have been developed using silver-plated polyamide fibers as the core electrode, with a carbon black/polyurethane (CB/PU) conductive elastomer in the sheath, consisting of two layers with different CB/PU concentrations for increased sensitivity [38]. This work aimed to recognize six types of abnormal gait patterns associated with neurodegenerative disorders, using machine learning methods and 144-pixel sensor-array shoe insoles. The authors report strong fabric durability (10 000 cycles) among other advantages, but do not provide manufacturing cost information.

Another well-studied type of smart textiles with sensory capabilities is the triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs), which convert mechanical energy into electrical energy to improve device autonomy. The study of Wang et al. [39] has been noted for using PVDF and PA66-based nanofiber coaxial yarns to fabricate highly sensitive woven TENG textiles for real-time gait analysis and monitoring. To produce the yarns, the nanofibers were spun onto stainless steel strands pre-coated with a polyvinyl-alcohol adhesive. The coating contained silver nanowires and liquid metals, improving the conductive and antibacterial properties of the yarn.

The use of smart textiles offers significant advantages, with high sensitivity, increased fabric durability, and fast response times being the most common. Although some manufacturing processes are simple and scalable, leading to relatively lower production costs, they can still require techniques based on expensive equipment or materials, such as graphene-based coatings, for the final product.

A viable alternative that offers the advantage of reducing the cost of sensors through the use of more cost-effective materials and fabrication methods is described in [16]. The method is very close to our approach, utilizing stainless steel conductive flexible threads to sew interdigitated capacitive (IDC) sensor patterns on fabrics.

In general, minimizing the cost of embedded sensors reduces the overall cost for an eventual product and makes it affordable to a potential patient. This serves as the main inspiration in this study, where an inexpensive prototype pair of insoles with embedded textile-based capacitive sensors is introduced. The sensors are designed and developed to address the challenges of gait phase recognition, as is the case with pressure sensors. A dataset is collected using pairs of the presented insoles, where volunteers were asked

to perform simple walking exercises. The accumulated data were subsequently utilized to train a long short-term memory (LSTM)-based neural network model that predicts the gait phase that takes place during human walking. The presented work focuses on predicting gait phases during straight-line walking at different paces. Its effectiveness is demonstrated, offering a practical and affordable approach for gait analysis that comprises a viable alternative to expensive, commercially available solutions.

In summary, the contributions are the following.

- 1) A novel, inexpensive prototype pair of capacitive sensor-based insoles with IMUs is introduced.
- 2) A publicly available dataset that was collected from volunteers who used the pairs of insoles to perform simple walking exercises.
- 3) The performance of the insoles is demonstrated on the collected dataset, using an LSTM-based deep learning approach that performs gait phase recognition during straight walking.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. In Section II, the materials and details for the fabrication of the prototype, the collected dataset, and the gait phase recognition method are presented. Section III contains the training procedure that was followed, the experiments conducted, the metrics that were used, and the results from the experiments, while in Section IV, the results, performance, and limitations of the presented approach are discussed. This article concludes with Section V where the possible applications and future steps are cited.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Insoles Fabrication and Hardware

Off-the-shelf insoles were purchased, and 28 AWG wires were fed through them in five set locations corresponding to front left, front right, middle left, middle right, and heel, color coded. Silver-based conductive thread (SilverTech 150) was used with an industrial embroidery machine (JCZA 0109-550, ZSK, Germany) to form pads on the top side of the insole, as can be seen in Fig. 1. The insoles were characterized using an HRM-300 optical profilometer (Huvitz, Republic of Korea). Additionally, impedance spectroscopy in the range of 1 MHz–1 GHz was conducted, with the goal of analyzing the relative permittivity of the latex insole. Hioki IM3580A (Hioki, Japan) was used for the aforementioned experiment. Up to this point, the cost per insole was less than 0.6€. From then onward, the insole lines are fed through an MPR121 IC, which is a 12-channel capacitive sensor controller. The MPR121 board communicates with an Arduino Nano 33 IoT microcontroller via C protocol in this prototyping stage. This microcontroller features onboard Wi-Fi and an IMU, and for this work, it was programmed to transmit data directly to the Arduino Cloud through a Wi-Fi hotspot set up on a smartphone and to be powered by a powerbank to allow for untethered operation. A 3-D-printed enclosure was also designed for this purpose (Fig. 1).

The embroidery process introduces parallel conductive lines in the latex foam insoles, orthogonal to the single capacitive electrode embroidered on the surface. The main detection event is a consequence of the proximity change between the embroidered electrodes and the foot itself. The

Fig. 1. Exploded view of the embroidered latex insole with the electrode pad (top). The prototype pair of insoles with the five embedded capacitive sensors (down left). Both insoles are depicted to be connected with the sensor controller and the Arduino chips; however, during data collection, each insole was connected to its own pair of chips, which was placed within a 3-D-printed box that was strapped around the foot (down right). A power bank per foot powers the equipment.

capacitance measured on each sensing channel is the total capacitance to ground. This total capacitance is the combination of background parasitic capacitance to ground (C_b) and object in proximity (in this case foot) induced capacitance to ground (C_x). The variation in proximity is detected by comparing the real-time capacitance change (the 2nd level filtered electrode output) against the baseline value. When this deviation surpasses the programmed threshold, the system flags either a touch (lower distance to the coupled object) or a release (increase in distance to the coupled object) event in the status register. Both touch and release thresholds can be independently configured for each electrode, allowing electrode-specific tuning. On the microscopic scale, as a consequence of the embroidery process itself, microscopic capacitive cells affect the output of the transducing element. The interwoven conductive fibers, separated by the porous insole substrate and the air gaps within the embroidery, effectively form a distributed network of capacitor plates. When analyzing the behavior at the microscale, three parameters influence the capacitance through a complex interplay: plate separation (d), effective area (A), and relative permittivity (ϵ_r). For plate separation (d), under vertical load, the compressible substrate and entrapped air pockets deform, reducing the effective distance between adjacent conductive fibers. This decrease in separation leads to an increase in capacitance. For effective area (A), the embroidery structure creates overlapping regions of conductive fibers. When pressure is applied, deformation of

TABLE I
STATISTICS OF THE COLLECTED DATASET

Statistic	Age (Years)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Shoe Size (EU)
Mean	35	167	74	41.9
Median	34.5	173	79	43
Range	21 - 48	162 - 181	61 - 94	37 - 44

the textile fibers increases the degree of fiber-to-fiber contact and overlap, thereby increasing the effective electrode area contributing to charge storage.

For dielectric constant (ϵ), the porous latex foam insole and the air trapped between fibers act as the dielectric. Upon compression, the air fraction decreases and more of the solid polymer or textile matrix fills the space, resulting in a higher effective dielectric constant. The combined effect of these three parameters leads to a sensitive modulation of capacitance with applied vertical pressure. At rest, the fibers form loosely coupled capacitive cells with relatively high separation and low overlap. With loading, localized deformation dynamically alters the microscopic geometry, causing measurable capacitance shifts. The MPR121 IC captures these changes, filters noise at three levels, and provides stable digital readouts that reflect the mechanical loading state of each embroidered pad [40]. The pad's 2nd-level filtered output is the measurement of the capacitive sensor. The 3rd-level filtered output is the capacitance baseline, and when compared to the 2nd-level output, the resulting deviation can determine, using a threshold, whether a touch or release of the pad has occurred. The analog value of voltage from the pads is converted to digital before filtering, so both filtered outputs are measured in ADC counts (levels) and stored in 10-bit registers, where the maximum value is 1023.

Although the price of the replaceable insole system is around 0.6€, it is necessary to investigate the lifespan of the transducing element. For this purpose, a tribology measurement was performed. The test conditions were as follows. High-density polyethylene (HDPE) balls were used to test the resilience of the embroidered electrodes. A force of 2 N was applied, with a stroke of 4 mm. The sliding speed was 8 mm/s at a frequency of 1 Hz. A total of 1000 cycles were executed, and after 250 cycles, the sheet resistance was measured. The device used for tribology measurement was the UTS TRIBILOG (UTS Scientific Instruments, Turkey). The sheet resistance was measured to evaluate how the conductivity of the electrode pads decreases with wear. An increase in electrode resistance has a direct effect on the time constant, as a higher resistance increases the time it takes for the capacitor to charge or discharge. Additionally, higher electrode resistance also increases the dielectric loss tangent. It is important to note that the tribology experiments were conducted on dry samples and on samples with artificial sweat (pH 6) applied to them. The size of these pads was 1 × 3 cm.

B. Dataset Description

The dataset has been collected from a sample of 20 healthy volunteers (7 women and 13 men), with no noticeable walking impairments. The statistics of the sample are shown in Table I. The equipment had been tightly strapped around the feet of each volunteer, as shown in Fig. 1. Each volunteer was asked to perform a simple walking exercise, which has also

TABLE II
TYPES OF GAIT EVENTS RECORDED IN THE DATASET

Event	Description
FOF	Foot is flat on the floor
HER	Heel rises from the floor after FOF
TOF	Toes leave the floor after HER
HES	Heel strikes the floor after TOF
TOS	Toes contact the floor after TOF
TOR	Toes rise from the floor after FOF
HOF	Heel leaves the floor after TOR
FOFF	An FOF that occurs immediately after a TOF, without an intermediate HES
TOFF	A TOF that occurs immediately after FOF, without intermediate HER

Fig. 2. Synchronization of HES events with the heel sensor measurements.

been used in relevant literature for similar data collection. Their lower body was also being video recorded to aid the data annotation process. Specifically, from a standing position, the volunteer walks 10 m in a straight line, then turns around, and walks back to the starting point. The exercise was performed three times, and the volunteer was instructed to walk each time using a different walking pace, choosing between slow, normal, and fast. The different walking paces are determined by the volunteer, as is common practice across the literature.

The resulting dataset was annotated using video footage from the exercises, regarding the observed gait events that took place at each moment. The annotating convention from the Smart-Insole dataset [10] was followed in this dataset, which means that the label of a timestamp/data-point depends on the last gait event that occurred, and each event holds until a new one takes place. The recorded gait events and their description are presented in Table II. The occurrence of event initiates the start of the event phase of the same type; thus, the HER event initiates the HER phase that persists until the next event occurrence. An example of this is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3 contains an example of the normalized analog-to-digital signals produced from all the sensors during walking, along with the annotations across time. A refining step took place after the data collection phase. Having the Arduino controller programmed to achieve a sampling rate of 12 Hz, the samples were interpolated to reach a rate of approximately 45 Hz. This step was applied for better accuracy during the annotation process because the recorded videos were shot at 25 frames/s. The sensor signals were then synchronized with the observed events in the videos. This was necessary because each measurement in the signal is sent directly to Arduino Cloud over the Internet, which incurs transmission

Fig. 3. Visualization of the five capacitive sensor signals across time during walking. The dots represent a sensor's normalized ADC level measured for each moment.

delays because each measurement is assigned a timestamp when stored on the Cloud. The delays were calculated manually using the observed HES events and the relevant measurements from the heel sensor signal. This type of event was selected because it is the easiest to identify by observing the produced sensor signals. The HES event takes place when the heel strikes the floor, which in turn corresponds to a steep downturn in the heel sensor signal. The transmission delay is the time difference between the timestamp of the observed event and the timestamp of the downturn in the signal. In other words, it is the time difference between the actual occurrence of the event and the moment the sensor measurement was stored on the Arduino Cloud. To synchronize, the HER-FOF-HES phase sequence has to be shifted so that the difference is eliminated, resulting in the signal presented in Fig. 2. The delays vary from 1 to 3.5 s, largely due to the amount of workload handled by the Arduino Cloud. This is despite the Arduino module utilizing a high-speed Internet connection with a bandwidth of 1 Gb/s and nearby Wi-Fi antennas to minimize intranet transmission delays.

C. Gait Phase Recognition Method

A deep learning method that uses a sequence-to-sequence recurrent neural network (seq2seq) [41] model has been employed for the evaluation of the prototype insoles. More specifically, its purpose is to translate a sequence of vectors that have been produced during walking, containing sensor measurements, to a sequence of gait events. The predicted gait event per timestamp pertains to the ongoing event (gait phase) that was predicted to have taken place or a new event. Seq2seq models consist of an encoder that encodes the input and a decoder that handles the translation of the encoded input. Both make use of LSTM modules with a hidden size of 128 and 2 layers. The measurements from a single insole per timestamp comprise a feature vector. A fixed-length sequence of those vectors composes the encoder input. The output of the model is a label value that corresponds to one of the four main gait events: FOF, HER, TOF, and HES. Fig. 4 contains a visualization of the gait phase recognition method. It must be noted that the secondary events that are included in the dataset are considered members of one of the main events: HOF and TOFF fall under the TOF class, and TOR, TOS, and FOFF fall under the FOF class. This decision was made because the occurrence of those events was small compared to the main ones. Balancing the data to also account for them would yield poor results and is a subject for future research.

Fig. 4. Architecture for gait phase recognition model. The model accepts a sequence of vectors containing the sensor values from each t_n point and predicts a label for per t_n .

A preprocessing step is applied on the data for the training process. The data from 16 subjects have been used for training purposes, and another 2 subjects have been used for evaluation and testing purposes. Each sequence is segmented into parts with a fixed length of 15 data points. A sliding window is also used for data augmentation in the training and validation sets. Thus, a pair of consecutive subsequences shares only three data points. Additionally, data that originate from the sensors of the right insole are inverted as a data augmentation measure. To handle the class imbalance problem that arises from the fact that some labels are underrepresented in the dataset, three hyperparameters are introduced. Their role is to filter out subsequences that are dominated by some labels, and their range of value is from 0 to 1. This task is performed only on the train and the validation sets.

The first hyperparameter defines the maximum percentage of combined TOF and FOF label representation within a subsequence. Those two labels usually dominate each sequence by occupying approximately 50% of the total assigned labels. The second hyperparameter handles the balance between HER and HES label representation. These two hyperparameters help the model focus on sequences that contain event transitions. However, as mentioned previously, TOF and FOF gait phases dominate the dataset due to the dominant, above a certain threshold. The concluding preprocessing step is the standardization of the sensor values. For this task, the relevant mean and standard deviation per subject, instead of the whole dataset, are used. That is because different individuals produce different max–min values from the capacitive sensors, but the signal patterns are similar, albeit in different ranges of values.

Fig. 5. Analog-to-digital voltage signal produced from the left foot heel sensor of three different volunteers during walking. The signal ADC levels range from 0 to 1023 for each data point across the sequence.

Fig. 5 showcases the output from the left heel sensor of three different volunteers during walking. Each signal exhibits its own maximum and minimum values from the capacitive sensors, owing to the different magnitudes of force exerted on the sensors due to each volunteer's weight. Nevertheless, the signal patterns remain similar, albeit within different value ranges. The sensor value per data point is the analog-to-digital conversion of the original voltage, represented as a 10-bit value.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Fig. 6 shows the optical profilometry of the latex foam insoles, before and after capacitive pad embroidery. The latex foam has a highly porous structure as seen in Fig. 6(a), which is compressed during the embroidery process. The silver threads pierce the latex foam, forming conductive parallel lines in the insole itself. The cross section of the capacitive pads can be seen in Fig. 6(b).

The results of impedance spectroscopy are shown in Fig. 7. Relative permittivity of the latex foam is shown in Fig. 7(a), and due to the high porosity of the latex foam, the air content is high and the dielectric constant is close to 1. The value is constant with a small shift toward 1.2 at the end of the measured frequency range. In Fig. 7(b), the change of capacitance with respect to frequency is shown. The capacitance of a capacitive structure filled with the latex foam insole has a similar trend, however slightly higher in value to that of a capacitive structure, same in dimensions, filled with air. This in turn further corroborates the high air content and porosity of the latex foam.

The change of sheet resistance with respect to the number of wear cycles is shown in Fig. 8(a). With the results shown in the previously mentioned figure, the change in the coefficient of friction goes hand in hand [Fig. 8(b)]. These figures show a negligible change in sheet resistance and coefficient of friction after 1000 cycles of wearing on the tribology machine. Expectedly, the samples with no Sweat showed a relatively higher sheet resistance, in comparison to the sample with artificial sweat administered on them. The relatively low change in sheet resistance and coefficient of friction could be associated with

the high porosity, consequently deformability of the insole electrode samples.

The capacitance change level is defined in the MPR121 proximity capacitive touch sensor datasheet. The change in capacitance with respect to the ADC count is given in the following equation:

$$\frac{dc}{d\text{ADC}_{\text{count}}} = \frac{I \cdot T}{(\text{ADC}_{\text{count}})^2} \cdot \frac{1024}{V_{\text{DD}}} = \frac{C}{\text{ADC}_{\text{count}}} \quad (1)$$

where I , T , and C denote the charge current, charge time, and capacitance, respectively; V_{DD} refers to the current source; and $\text{ADC}_{\text{count}}$ represents the change in ADC levels.

Fig. 9 shows the ADC level change with respect to the distance of the second electrode (in our application, this is the sole of the foot). To quantify this change, we used the 34SC-2 Tension testing system (Instron, USA) to accurately move the second electrode (aluminum patch attached to the machine handle) to specific distances away from the capacitive proximity touch sensor. A significant drop in ADC level happens around 1 mm, showing that there is an increase in capacitance on the sensing channel when a certain distance threshold is crossed.

Additionally, compression tests were performed using the same apparatus (Instron Tension testing system), with forces applied ranging from 100 to 2000 N. As contact between the measurement device and the surface of the sample is the condition for applying compressive force (in terms of pressure), the capacitive proximity touch sensor showed a low ADC level at 100 N and remained at low levels with negligible variation until 2000 N.

While not directly measured, the sensor drift is internally compensated using MPR121's baseline tracking and filtering sequence. Additionally, standardization of response was done for each subject. Even though long-term wearing comfort was not quantitatively analyzed, qualitatively, during the execution of the gait phase data acquisition, none of the 20 volunteers reported having problems or discomfort.

The influence of sweating on signal stability was analyzed by dropping 3 mL of artificial sweat (same as the one used in the wear analysis experiment) on specific parts of the insoles, around the electrodes. The response in each stage is shown in Fig. 10. After artificial sweat application, the electrodes change in ADC level drops, and with the subsequent spreading of the liquid between two neighboring electrodes, they become short circuited. This leads to a shared change in ADC level between the shorted electrodes. After the sweat influence experiment was complete, the insoles were put in a sintering oven (Memmert, Germany) to dry at 45 °C for 1 h, to increase the drying process. After the drying process was finished, the insoles became functional again, and each electrode pad worked separately. It is important to note that this test confirms that if the insole becomes wet, either with sweat or rainwater, after drying, it reverts back to a fully functional system. While the insoles are wet, depending on the degree of wetness, they can detect changes in the gait.

Moreover, sensor drift was analyzed through baseline analysis, in which 500 steps were recorded of normal gait and the baseline was extracted through a moving average filter with a window size of 301. The analysis showed that there is a slight average drift of 27 ADC levels; however,

Fig. 6. Optical profilometry of (a) latex foam insole before embroidery and (b) latex foam insole after embroidery.

Fig. 7. Impedance spectroscopy of the latex foam insole. (a) Relative permittivity. (b) Capacitance with respect to frequency.

Fig. 8. Tribology measurement results. (a) Sheet resistance changes with respect to the number of cycles. (b) Coefficient of friction changes with respect to the number of cycles.

this can be attributed to possible variations in gait as well. Most importantly, the slight average drift of 27 ADC levels is negligible in comparison to the average difference between

an activated capacitive touch sensor and a nonactivated one (average value of 142). Additionally, the drift, when compared between five different sensing electrodes, changes

Fig. 9. Dependence of ADC level with respect to the distance of the second electrode.

Fig. 10. Change of ADC level in different stages of the insole wetting and drying sequence.

Fig. 11. Change of ADC level over a sequence of 500 steps.

between 11 and 48, depending on the used sensor. This variability does not affect the system performance in a significant way. Fig. 11 shows the response of one sensor, the baseline of the sensor, and the range in which the values of gait are from the depicted sensor, over a range of 500 steps.

For the training process of the phase prediction model, the Adam optimizer was used and the learning rate was set to 1×10^{-4} for 25 epochs and then reduced to 1×10^{-5} for another 5, for a total of 30 training epochs, with a batch size of 128. The negative log likelihood loss was selected for the process. The data from volunteers no. 18 and 19 were used for evaluation and testing purposes, while the data from all the other volunteers, except for volunteers no. 8 and 20, were used for training. Regarding volunteer no. 8, it was noticed through the data measurements that there was a small limp on the right foot that was not stepping correctly; thus, the recorded data could not be used. In the case of volunteer no. 20, the 3-D-printed clip that was holding the equipment strapped

on the right foot snapped during the recording session, resulting in incomplete data collection. However, in both cases, the recorded data were preserved for good measure. The hyperparameter values, for TOF-FOF maximum percentage within the sequence, were set to 0.65; for HER-HES balance, it was set to 0.6, and the lower threshold for TOF-FOF dominant sequences was set to 0.85. Along with the data from the five capacitive sensors, $acceleration_x$, $acceleration_y$, and $angular_z$ from the IMU measurements were used for training.

The k -fold cross-validation method was selected to determine the best set of parameters–hyperparameters for the trained model, using $k = 6$ and the available data from 18 subjects (exempting no. 8 and 20). The method splits the whole dataset into k folds/parts, using all but one for training and the remaining for evaluation, with the final score being the average value from the k evaluation runs. *Macro-averaged F1* score was used as an evaluation metric, due to the imbalanced nature of the test sets. The score corresponds to the unweighted mean of the $F1$ scores per class of the problem, where the $F1$ score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall of a trained model. *Precision* expresses how many of the predicted samples were predicted correctly within a class, while *recall* expresses how many of the class total samples were predicted correctly. Like the $F1$ score, both are expressed either as a value from 0 to 1 or as a percentage and are calculated separately per class. *Accuracy* was also used as a metric. It mirrors the amount of correct predictions as a ratio of all predictions made.

Using the best configuration, a model was trained and then evaluated on the test set to showcase its capability in a real-world scenario. For the real-world scenario, we choose to produce results for each of the three different walking paces and one final test using all three paces. The results from cross validation and the test set are presented in Table III. The table also includes the results for precision and recall per exercise as well as the $F1$ scores for the individual classes. A visualization of the predicted gait phase against the ground truth (GT) on the test set is observed in Figs. 12 and 13. Finally, Fig. 14 depicts the confusion matrices, quantifying the visualizations from the previous two figures but also emphasizing the imbalanced nature of the class samples.

IV. DISCUSSION

The performance of the gait phase prediction method is clearly satisfactory with *accuracy* of 90% and most importantly, an *F1 Macro* score of 87.1% given the imbalanced nature of real-world data, in favor of the TOF and FOF events. The imbalance is visually noticed in every presented figure that depicts the signals across time, where TOF and FOF have a greater degree of representation, but is actually quantified in Fig. 14. Data points that relate to TOF and FOF phases individually are more than triple the size of each of the other two main events. Incorrect classifications of data points exist concentrated around phase transitions and can be observed in Figs. 12 and 13.

Fig. 12 presents an example of mislabeling during prediction. The GT and the predicted (Pred) gait phases are depicted in the upper and lower plots, respectively. The GT sequence starts with a toe-off (TOF) phase followed by a foot-flat (FOF). This sequence of phases corresponds

TABLE III
EVALUATION OF THE PREDICTION MODEL FOR THE DIFFERENT WALKING PACES IN THE TEST SETS AND OVERALL

Exercise	Accuracy	F1 Macro	Precision	Recall	F1-HER	F1-TOF	F1-HES	F1-FOF
Gait - Fast	88.6%	85.8%	86.4%	85.4%	78.0%	93.9%	81.1%	90.3%
Gait - Normal	89.8%	87.0%	87.9%	86.3%	79.2%	93.9%	82.9%	92.0%
Gait - Slow	90.9%	88.0%	87.5%	88.6%	80.5%	94.4%	83.5%	93.4%
Gait - All	90.0%	87.1%	87.3%	87.0%	79.4%	94.1%	82.7%	92.3%
k-Fold Validation	87.3%	84.0%	84.8%	84.0%	78.5%	92.7%	75.8%	89.1%

Fig. 12. Example of mislabeled TOF to FOF phase transition during prediction.

Fig. 13. Case of imprecision in the prediction of phase transition (start–end of the successive gait phases).

to a step where the whole plantar surface touches the floor at the same time. This contrasts with a usual step where the heel area precedes the front part of the foot when touching the floor. The same sensor lines (normalized) are depicted in both plots, in red for the heel, blue for the frontal right sensor, and magenta for the frontal left one. The difference between the first step and the next two steps is noticeable in the traces of the frontal sensors in the plot;

however, the model predicted an HES phase that did not take place. Immediate transition from TOF to FOF (or FOF to FOF) in this case since, as mentioned in Section II-C, FOF events as a secondary type of event fall under the FOF label) is not a common occurrence. Addressing errors like this requires more instances of the phase transition, therefore, larger datasets. Despite this, however, the rest of the sequence is predicted correctly.

Fig. 14. Confusion matrices for the different walking paces presented in Table III and the test set overall depict the predicted events versus the actual ones, per sequence data point. The event labels correspond to FOF (foot is flat on the floor), HER (heel rises from the floor after FOF), TOF (toes leave the floor after HER), and HES (heel strikes the floor after TOF and is usually followed by FOF).

Fig. 13 presents a case of mismatching in the duration of the predicted phases. The depicted trace in red corresponds to the heel sensor normalized measurements. Steps (the areas between the blue boxes) are predicted to take place correctly; however, a small imprecision is observed in some cases, regarding the point of phase transition. Classification errors like this cause a deviation in the correct prediction of the boundaries of a phase, of the order of a few hundredths of a second. While the desirable precision is something that depends on the nature of the problem to be solved, the imprecision is still a problem that requires attention. The sensors presented in this work function pretty much as FSRs would do, in the sense that the recorded values change gradually and not in an instant, like a touch sensor would do. Hence, an important thing ought to be mentioned about the precision of the phase transition relates to the synchronization of the sensor measurements during the data preprocessing step. The procedure sought to address the problem of the desynchronized data. The manual synchronization was done at the level of a gait cycle, based on the HES event of each cycle as mentioned earlier, however, that does not warrant that the measurements between successive HES events are not subjected to any fluctuating transmission delays. This issue can only be solved by minimizing the data transmission/storage time as much as possible.

Another thing worth noting in Table III is the results regarding the different walking paces. It seems that the slower the pace, the better the results, which is something that has been mentioned multiple times in other works in the reviewed literature. This is probably owed to the fact that the foot's movement is recorded with greater resolution by the sensors given enough time; thus, the aspects that define the start–end of the different phases are defined more clearly through the presence of more samples.

A limitation of the prediction model is that there is no provision for the nonmain events, which in the present implementation fall under the main events due to their small presence in the dataset. It is also important to include the nonmain events in the predictions for cases where gait analysis is performed for patients with motor problems, where they can help in revealing deviations in the gait pattern.

Compared to existing approaches, our research demonstrates an affordable and practical method for gait analysis. The low cost of the required materials, as well as the sensor manufacturing process, keeps the unit production cost minimal

since it can be applied directly to commercially available low-cost insoles. By contrast, methods reported in the literature often require more expensive materials or elaborate techniques for fabricating electronic sensors, additional layers for sensor placement, or textile fibers that comprise multiple layers. The presented sensor production processes in those works are, in many cases, more complex than simply embroidering textile sensors on fabric.

In general, embroidering the sensors directly onto the user's shoes is impractical for real-world use. It would require the user to either have the sensors embroidered on their shoes after they have bought them or buy specific shoes with pre-installed sensors. Both alternatives would probably increase the cost per unit significantly. For this reason, we embroidered our sensors on commercially available insoles so that both the insole and sensors can be replaced easily at low cost. IDC sensors constitute an alternative that can also be embroidered on fabrics [16] and are known to have higher sensitivity than the pad sensors that we use in our method. However, commercially available insoles—being inexpensive due to their materials—cannot guarantee the long-term preservation of the geometric structures that give IDC sensors their sensitivity advantage. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies that directly compare the two sensor designs; however, the pad sensors ought to be more durable given their simpler design. Our tests show that the sensitivity of pad sensors is sufficient for the task of gait analysis, as the pressure exerted by the human body weighs several tens of kilograms. The same amount of pressure would significantly shorten the lifespan of IDC sensors.

A key innovation in our approach is the use of the MPR121 controller. This component filters noise from the sensory signal and produces an output with multiple discrete levels, as shown in the signal diagrams. In contrast, an existing approach [16] reports capturing only up to three signal levels. The higher signal resolution allows recording of different pressure intensities on the sensor and provides richer data for deep learning-based pattern recognition. As a result, gait phase recognition accuracy improves, which may also help detect gait abnormalities linked to neurodegenerative diseases.

About the insole design and construction, further research regarding the scenarios of long-term insole use or using the insoles while partially completely wet, would be useful to assess the quality of gait phase prediction. In the presented implementation, the proposed device is powered using one power bank per leg; however, smaller batteries could be used

in a future improved version. In conclusion, the pair of insoles itself can be washed normally up to the thresholds of the insole material.

V. CONCLUSION

Overall, the prediction method succeeds as a proof of concept for the effectiveness of the presented sensor-based insoles and their viability as an alternative. The practical benefit of the insoles prototype versus commercial solutions is that it is cost-effective and affordable for gait analysis through telemedicine, with open-source software components, for both the hardware and the gait phase prediction model. The use of deep learning for the prediction makes it more versatile when compared to rule-based algorithms from the literature, especially with the abundance of available data nowadays. The above are especially important for elderly people who lack the ease of access to a healthcare specialist and need tele-rehabilitation solutions that help monitor their progress or reveal signs of developing neurodegenerative diseases.

Future improvements include enhancing data quality by minimizing the transmission delays and introducing more samples to represent secondary gait events. Regarding the prototype insoles, development plans include making the electronics compartment design less bulky. Additionally, the use of smaller batteries is being considered, with a focus on improving user experience and comfort.

INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

All participants have signed an informed consent form.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that have been used for the training/evaluation of the prediction model are publicly available; however, no identifying information on the study participants will be made available, in line with the applicable data protection regulation laws and ethics guidelines.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the article; or in the decision to publish the results.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Montero-Odasso, J. Verghese, O. Beauchet, and J. M. Hausdorff, "Gait and cognition: A complementary approach to understanding brain function and the risk of falling," *J. Amer. Geriatrics Soc.*, vol. 60, no. 11, pp. 2127–2136, Nov. 2012.
- [2] K. M. Esquivel, "Remote rehabilitation: A solution to overloaded & scarce health care systems," *TTEH*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–19, Aug. 2018.
- [3] L. D'arco, G. Mccalmont, H. Wang, and H. Zheng, "Application of smart insoles for recognition of activities of daily living: A systematic review," *ACM Trans. Comput. Healthcare*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–34, Jan. 2024.
- [4] A. Khan, O. Galarraga, S. Garcia-Salicetti, and V. Vigneron, "Deep learning for quantified gait analysis: A systematic literature review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 138932–138957, 2024.
- [5] I. P. I. Pappas, M. R. Popovic, T. Keller, V. Dietz, and M. Morari, "A reliable gait phase detection system," *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 113–125, Jun. 2001.
- [6] E. Sazonov, N. Hegde, R. C. Browning, E. L. Melanson, and N. A. Sazonova, "Posture and activity recognition and energy expenditure estimation in a wearable platform," *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Informat.*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 1339–1346, Jul. 2015.
- [7] R. Guo et al., "A shoe-integrated sensor system for long-term center of pressure evaluation," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 21, no. 23, pp. 27037–27044, Dec. 2021.
- [8] W. Anderson, Z. Choffin, N. Jeong, M. Callihan, S. Jeong, and E. Sazonov, "Empirical study on human movement classification using insole footwear sensor system and machine learning," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 7, p. 2743, Apr. 2022.
- [9] U. Manupibul, R. Tanthuwapathom, W. Jarumethitanont, P. Kaimuk, W. Limroongreungrat, and W. Charoensuk, "Integration of force and IMU sensors for developing low-cost portable gait measurement system in lower extremities," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 10653, Jun. 2023.
- [10] D. Chen, G. Asaeikheybari, H. Chen, W. Xu, and M.-C. Huang, "Ubiquitous fall hazard identification with smart insole," *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Informat.*, vol. 25, no. 7, pp. 2768–2776, Jul. 2021.
- [11] J. Lee et al., "Flexible smart insole and plantar pressure monitoring using screen-printed nanomaterials and piezoresistive sensors," *ACS Appl. Mater. Interface*, vol. 17, no. 33, pp. 47153–47161, Aug. 2025.
- [12] S. Bamberg, A. Y. Benbasat, D. M. Scarborough, D. E. Krebs, and J. A. Paradiso, "Gait analysis using a shoe-integrated wireless sensor system," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Technol. Biomed.*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 413–423, Jul. 2008.
- [13] Y. Dai, Y. Xie, J. Chen, S. Kang, L. Xu, and S. Gao, "A lamination-based piezoelectric insole gait analysis system for massive production for Internet-of-Health Things," *Int. J. Distrib. Sensor Netw.*, vol. 16, no. 3, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 155014772090543.
- [14] B. Latsch et al., "3D-printed piezoelectric PLA-based insole for event detection in gait analysis," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 24, no. 16, pp. 26472–26486, Aug. 2024.
- [15] M. Haescher, D. J. C. Matthies, G. Bieber, and B. Urban, "CapWalk: A capacitive recognition of walking-based activities as a wearable assistive technology," in *Proc. 8th ACM Int. Conf. Pervasive Technol. Rel. Assistive Environ.*, Jul. 2015, pp. 1–8.
- [16] M. Qasim Mehmood et al., "Textile-based washable multimode capacitive sensors for wearable applications," *IEEE J. Flexible Electron.*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 445–453, Oct. 2024.
- [17] G. Lan, D. Ma, W. Xu, M. Hassan, and W. Hu, "Capacitor-based activity sensing for kinetic-powered wearable IoTs," *ACM Trans. Internet Things*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–26, Mar. 2020.
- [18] K. Kong and M. Tomizuka, "A gait monitoring system based on air pressure sensors embedded in a shoe," *IEEE/ASME Trans. Mechatronics*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 358–370, Jun. 2009.
- [19] R. D. P. André, P. H. F. S. Diniz, and H. Fuks, "Bottom-up investigation: Human activity recognition based on feet movement and posture information," in *Proc. 4th Int. Workshop Sensor-Based Activity Recognit. Interact.*, Sep. 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [20] A. Prado, X. Cao, M. T. Robert, A. M. Gordon, and S. K. Agrawal, "Gait segmentation of data collected by instrumented shoes using a recurrent neural network classifier," *Phys. Med. Rehabil. Clinics North Amer.*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 355–366, May 2019.
- [21] P. H. Truong, S. You, S.-H. Ji, and G.-M. Jeong, "Wearable system for daily activity recognition using inertial and pressure sensors of a smart band and smart shoes," *Int. J. Comput. Commun. CONTROL*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 726–742, Feb. 2020.
- [22] N. Hegde and E. Sazonov, "SmartStep: A fully integrated, low-power insole monitor," *Electronics*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 381–397, Jun. 2014.
- [23] I. González, J. Fontecha, R. Hervás, and J. Bravo, "An ambulatory system for gait monitoring based on wireless sensorized insoles," *Sensors*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 16589–16613, Jul. 2015.
- [24] K. Key, S. Mason, and B. Kihei, "Analysis of activities based on a single-shoe equipped with force sensors," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Smart Cities Conf. (ISC)*, Sep. 2021, pp. 1–7.
- [25] M. Saito et al., "An in-shoe device to measure plantar pressure during daily human activity," *Med. Eng. Phys.*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 638–645, Jun. 2011.
- [26] J. S. Park, C. M. Lee, S.-M. Koo, and C. H. Kim, "Gait phase detection using force sensing resistors," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 20, no. 12, pp. 6516–6523, Jun. 2020.
- [27] J. C. Perez-Ibarra, A. A. G. Siqueira, and H. I. Krebs, "Identification of gait events in healthy and Parkinson's disease subjects using inertial sensors: A supervised learning approach," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 20, no. 24, pp. 14984–14993, Dec. 2020.
- [28] K. J. Merry et al., "Classifying sitting, standing, and walking using plantar force data," *Med. Biol. Eng. Comput.*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 257–270, Jan. 2021.
- [29] L. Song, C. Xiang, H. Guo, and S. Chen, "Activity recognition using multiplex limited penetrable visibility graph," *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.*, vol. 124, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 104880.

- [30] L. Wang et al., "Application challenges in fiber and textile electronics," *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 32, no. 5, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 1901971.
- [31] E. P. Scilingo, F. Lorussi, A. Mazzoldi, and D. De Rossi, "Strain-sensing fabrics for wearable kinaesthetic-like systems," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 460–467, Aug. 2003.
- [32] Y. Ma, D. Xing, M. Tian, L. Qu, X. Zhang, and X. Hu, "Multiwalled hollow polyurethane and graphene oxide/polyurethane fibers in Janus textiles for thermal management and sensors," *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.*, vol. 7, no. 19, pp. 22884–22894, Oct. 2024.
- [33] M. Zhou, W. Jiang, and J. Wang, "Design and manufacture of intelligent fabric-based insoles for disease prevention by monitoring plantar pressure," *Mater. Today Commun.*, vol. 37, Dec. 2023, Art. no. 107646.
- [34] M. Zhou, W. Jiang, and J. Wang, "Fabric-based insoles with self-equipped sensors for the foot's physiological signal monitoring," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 24, pp. 4496–4503, Feb. 2024.
- [35] C. Zhang et al., "Graphene sterically-wrapped textile piezoresistive sensors: A spray coating path for synergistically advancing sensitivity and response range," *Chem. Eng. J.*, vol. 495, Sep. 2024, Art. no. 153533.
- [36] K. Burch, S. Doshi, A. Chaudhari, E. Thostenson, and J. Higginson, "Estimating ground reaction force with novel carbon nanotube-based textile insole pressure sensors," *Wearable Technol.*, vol. 4, Mar. 2023, Art. no. e8.
- [37] F. Wang et al., "Industrially scalable textile sensing interfaces for extended artificial tactile and human motion monitoring without compromising comfort," *ACS Appl. Mater. Interface*, vol. 16, no. 13, pp. 16788–16799, Apr. 2024.
- [38] X. Yin et al., "High-resolution pressure sensing insole via sensitivity-tunable fibers towards gait recognition," *Chem. Eng. J.*, vol. 505, Feb. 2025, Art. no. 159841.
- [39] Y. Wang et al., "Scalable and ultra-sensitive nanofibers coaxial Yarn-Woven triboelectric nanogenerator textile sensors for real-time gait analysis," *Adv. Sci.*, vol. 11, no. 28, Jul. 2024, Art. no. 2401436.
- [40] X. Lin et al., "Design and construction of 1D/2D/3D fabric-based wearable micro-supercapacitors," *J. Power Sources*, vol. 560, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 232712.
- [41] I. Sutskever, O. Vinyals, and Q. V. Le, "Sequence to sequence learning with neural networks," 2014, *arXiv:1409.3215*.

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